

Exploring the Moderating Effect of Knowledge Sharing on the Relationship between Stakeholder Management Process and Sustainability of Corporate Social Responsibility Projects, in Western Kenya

¹ Calistus Adema Luhombo, ² Kevin Ogonji Muluka

¹ Adjunct Lecturer, Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, Kenya

² Adjunct Lecturer, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10935332>

Published Date: 06-April-2024

Abstract: Within Kenya's research landscape, the concept of project sustainability is increasingly emerging as a widespread issue in both the private and public sectors. Despite witnessing substantial advancements in project implementation, the post-implementation phase often falls short in terms of sustainability, resulting in a meagre number of projects being able to maintain their longevity. This study aimed to contribute to the expanding body of knowledge by investigating the impact of knowledge sharing as a moderator on the association between Stakeholder Identification, Stakeholder Communication, Stakeholder Engagement, and Stakeholder Empowerment on the sustainability of Corporate Social Responsibility Programs (CSRPs) in Technical and Vocational Education and Training institutions (TVETs) in western Kenya. Review of literature and identification of knowledge gaps formed the basis of the conceptual model and hypotheses. The findings revealed that knowledge sharing plays a crucial role in moderating the stakeholder management process and ensuring the long-term sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs. In conclusion, the study establishes that the joint effect of stakeholder identification and stakeholder engagement, moderated by knowledge sharing, has a more substantial influence on the sustainability of CSRPs compared to the separate effects of the predictor variables. To enhance the sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs, the study recommends providing stakeholders with training on effective stakeholder communication and engagement, thereby strengthening the stakeholder management process.

Keywords: Knowledge Sharing, Stakeholder Identification, Stakeholder Communication, Stakeholder Engagement, Stakeholder Empowerment, Sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Foss, Husted, and Michailova (2010), knowledge sharing is the exchanging of knowledge between two people with the aim of converting personal knowledge into organizational knowledge, which will enhance both parties' ability to absorb information and innovate. Additionally, two people are observed exchanging knowledge: one transmits knowledge, while the other absorbs it (Abdelwhab, Panneer selvam, Paris & Gunasekaran, 2019). As knowledge is never truly shared, human capital and interpersonal interactions are the focus (Oliveira & Pinheiro, 2020). The recipient understands it in the context of their own experience because it is situated within a particular framework (Rubel *et al.*, 2021). Getting people to integrate and share their knowledge is a major barrier when it comes to facilitating knowledge sharing within organizations, which can be challenging (Lam & Lambermont-Ford, 2010). Tamsah, Ansar, Ilyas, Yusriadi, and Farida (2020) opine that although knowledge sharing and transfer are sometimes used synonymously, there is a significant difference between the

two: transfer involves focus, a distinct goal, and unidirectionality, whereas knowledge sharing can occur inadvertently and in multiple directions without a clear purpose.

Foss *et al.* (2010) assert four reasons why it is critical to prioritize knowledge sharing; since it's intended to transform individual knowledge into organizational knowledge, it provides a rich environment for examining problems pertaining to construct level. Enhancement of innovation and absorption capacity, among other capabilities, can be attained through the dissemination of knowledge. Sharing knowledge has the potential to produce a long-term competitive advantage since it may be a significant precondition for problem-solving efforts. Third, because not every organization engages in the creation of new knowledge, it is challenging to imagine contemporary organizational life without knowledge sharing procedures in place. And last, explanations and forecasts about how knowledge sharing can be guided in desired directions continue to pique the interest of executives and other practicing managers.

Empirical evidence, points to a strong correlation between the uptake of firms' performance practices and the adoption of knowledge management practices, as demonstrated by the work of: (1) Abdelwhab Ali (2019); (2) Tamsah (2020); (3) Watetu (2015). (Abdelwhab Ali *et al.*, 2019; Tamsah *et al.*, 2020; Watetu, 2015). More specifically, the results suggest that knowledge sharing in organizations is positively impacted by information systems, trust and communication, organizational structure and rewards (Zhao *et al.*, 2020). Wang and Noe (2010) identify five focus areas for knowledge-sharing research: interpersonal and team characteristics, organizational context, individual characteristics, cultural characteristics, and motivational factors. Fairness, identification and transparency are seen as ways to encourage individuals to provide personal knowledge and help community members share their knowledge. (Fayyaz *et al.*, 2021).

Both implicit and explicit practices of sharing knowledge contribute to performance and innovation. According to Oliveira and Pinheiro (2020), explicit knowledge sharing has a greater impact on financial performance and the speed of innovation. On the other hand, Wang, and Wang (2012) suggest that implicit knowledge sharing, which is not explicitly expressed, has a more significant influence on operational performance and the quality of innovation. Reychav and Weisberg (2010) further argue that the intention to share explicit knowledge has an equal and direct effect on detailed knowledge-sharing behavior. In contrast, the intention to share implicit knowledge has a direct impact on knowledge-sharing behavior and a less indirect effect on the intention to share explicit knowledge. Pinjani and Palvia (2013) argue that limited shared knowledge leads to decreased interaction among individuals. When team members are unable to interact effectively, the integration of knowledge becomes less probable (Halisah *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, effectively managing team knowledge positively affects the success of the team's project. Furthermore, trust and dependence play a significant role in facilitating knowledge sharing, ultimately contributing to improved team project performance (Park & Lee, 2016).

Santos *et al.* (2012) identified several major barriers to knowledge sharing. These barriers include inadequate information technology, difficulties in the codification process, lack of strategy among workers, lack of initiative, and insufficient resources and time. However, by effectively utilizing organizational knowledge resources, it is possible to ensure that the right knowledge is accessible to the right individuals at the right time. This, in turn, enhances the quality of decision making and problem solving. The study also establishes a connection between knowledge sharing and stakeholder management process and Corporate Social Responsibility Programs (CSRPs). This is because the principles of knowledge sharing impact both project ownership (sustainability) and knowledge management (stakeholder management process). Additionally, the study conceptualizes knowledge sharing as encompassing trust, information systems, and motivation, as proposed by Foss *et al.*, (2010). Society provides business with the resources and the environment to make profit. In return society expects business organizations to be good corporate citizens, which obeys the laws of the land and refrains from activities that have negative social consequences. Business organizations should not just exist to make profits but should be involved in finding solutions to society's problems and improve the quality of life for its workers and the communities in which they exist (Oloo, 2003:15).

The Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) concept, as defined by the World Business Council for Sustainable Development, involves businesses committing to sustainable development by collaborating with employees, their families, the local community, and society as a whole to enhance their quality of life (Pearce, 2003:60). Different interpretations of CSR lead to varying organizational policies (Tucker and Henkel, 1992; Mc Ewan, 2001). One perspective suggests that companies should focus solely on generating profits for shareholders. In this scenario, corporate leaders and employees aim to maximize profits for shareholders, who can then choose to allocate dividends towards public causes like education, healthcare, childcare, or poverty alleviation. Several justifications exist for channeling a portion of a company's earnings towards public welfare (Pearce, 2003). The profitability of businesses relies partly on the approval of the public towards their operations and the support of the infrastructure they utilize. It is within the best interest of companies to act as

responsible corporate citizens. By engaging in public issues, a company is likely to improve its reputation. Furthermore, such engagement can also lead to better business outcomes. Managers have the opportunity to contribute to societal improvement by encouraging their company to allocate resources towards projects that benefit the public (Cavangh *et al.*, 2002:132). This study aims to explore CSR as a concept that guides companies in integrating social and environmental concerns into their operations and relationships with stakeholders voluntarily (Fuchs and Leonhard, 2007: 147).

The Encyclopedia of Knowledge Management provides a definition of knowledge sharing as the exchange of knowledge between two individuals: one who communicates knowledge and one who assimilates it (Schwartz, 2006). In knowledge sharing, the emphasis is on human capital and the interaction between individuals, as knowledge cannot be simply shared. It exists within a context, and the receiver interprets it based on their own background (Paulin & Suneson, 2012). Facilitating knowledge sharing within organizations is a challenging task, as the willingness of individuals to share and integrate their knowledge is a significant barrier (Lam & Lambermont-Ford, 2010). A key distinction between knowledge sharing and knowledge transfer (terms that are sometimes used interchangeably) is that transfer implies a focus, a clear objective, and unidirectionality, while knowledge can be shared in unintended ways, with multiple directions and without a specific objective (King, 2011).

Community Participation refers to the willingness of individuals to contribute their knowledge in relation to company-led CSR initiatives. Santos, Soares, and Carvalho (2012) have identified several barriers to knowledge sharing, including the codification process, inadequate information technology, lack of initiative and strategy among workers, and limited time and resources. However, effectively utilizing organizational knowledge resources can ensure that the right knowledge is accessible to the right people at the right time, thereby enhancing problem-solving and decision-making capabilities. This study establishes a connection between knowledge sharing and bridging the gap between academia, industry, and the community, as the principles of knowledge sharing impact both project ownership (sustainability) and knowledge management (stakeholder management process) (Luhombo *et al.*, 2019). The objective of this study was to examine the moderating effect of knowledge sharing on the influence of stakeholder identification, stakeholder communication, stakeholder engagement, and stakeholder empowerment on the sustainability of SCPs in TVETS in western Kenya. Detailed findings are presented in the subsequent subsections. Reviewed studies in the field of knowledge sharing focused on the knowledge management practices of organizations (Halisah *et al.*, 2021; Maende, 2021; Shehab *et al.*, 2018, 2019) but the critical link with project sustainability has been missing which this study attempts to address. The study identified knowledge sharing as a moderating variable in the relationship between stakeholder management process and CSRP sustainability.

Theoretical Background

The theory used in this research was Institutional Theory. According to Nelson Phillips, the creator of institutional theory, institutionalization—the act of forming an institution—is the foundation of sustainable growth (Schneiberg & Lounsbury, 2017). A deeper and more resilient part of social organization is addressed by institutional theory. It is motivated by the fact that various organizations, even when they operate in radically diverse circumstances, frequently share structural similarities (Amenta & Ramsey, 2010). It takes into account the methods by which norms, rules, routines, and schemas are formed as standards for social conduct (Kariuki, 2014).

Institutions have a restricting effect on organizations known as isomorphism, which makes organizations within the same population resemble other organizations that deal with comparable environmental conditions (Toner & Martins, 2021). Individuals act according to convention rather than because they are required to by law (Kariuki, 2014). After mapping 496 dyadic interactions pertaining to 17 innovative product concepts over the course of a 14-month on-site field study in a multinational firm, Deichmann *et al.* (2021) found that knowledge sharing may be explained by the ties between people being either strong or weak, rather than intermediate. They also found that the tie strength affects the length and scope of knowledge sharing in concept talks, depending on the qualities of the idea itself.

The benefits offered to the public and the institutions' compatibility with the culture and values of its subjects are major factors in determining their stability (Schneiberg & Soule, 2005). When compared to other sectors, a systematic review conducted by Al-Kurdi *et al.* (2020) revealed that contributions to the understanding of knowledge sharing in higher education institutions are low. Future study directions are suggested by the review, which covers organizational, cultural, behavioral, and technological issues at various levels. The failure of institutional theory to see a project as satisfying a shared need and naturally uniting individuals that leads to project sustainability is its flaw. It frequently asks for combining other ideas or doing more process-oriented studies.

According to Herold (2018), although recent research recognizes that stakeholders may have an impact on institutional logics, it is conceptually vague and has limitations when it comes to classifying stakeholder influences at the business level. He shows that institutional and stakeholder theory offer, on many levels, a theoretical platform to investigate the influences on sustainability reporting based on institutional and stakeholder constructions. As a result, the stakeholder theory in the study addressed the issue. Since institutionalizing sustainability goes beyond addressing a shared need and necessitates a process of knowledge sharing among stakeholders, institutional theory was chosen for the study.

Conceptual Framework

The study highlights the relationship between stakeholder management process (Independent variable) and sustainability of CSRPs (Dependent variable). While knowledge sharing was conceptualized as a moderator in this relationship as presented in Figure 1.1.

Effective knowledge sharing is necessary to improve individual behavior, and the willingness to exchange knowledge and the results of such exchange may indirectly include an individual's willingness to share their knowledge (Shehab *et al.*, 2019). Sharing knowledge with members (stakeholders) often helps organizations improve their work experience and ultimately achieve more success; in the study, it was related to the extensive participation of stakeholders in projects. Maende's (2021) study showed that organizational structure could positively moderate the relationship between knowledge management practices and employee performance when employees in public universities in Kenya felt empowered and when there were consistent communication channels to facilitate the flow of knowledge between employees. increases teamwork and cooperation.

Knowledge management is sensitive to the silent dimension, which is partially or fully unconscious (Li *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, aspects of the power, interest and recognition of a network are often difficult to separate from its human owner, and are therefore intangible in nature, making identification of stakeholders difficult (Maende, 2021). The consensus is that stakeholder power and interest are expected to have a strong correlation with stakeholder management strategies (Nguyen & Mohamed, 2020). A study by Nyambura (2018) found that all independent variables in the study were not significant predictors. On the performance of Kenyan manufacturing firms excluding organizational characteristics. However, the model for the joint moderating effect of ICT use on the relationship between supply chain risks and firm performance was found to be significant, which may have been due to organizational characteristics. The moderating effect of knowledge sharing is significant when it comes to stakeholder management and sustainability, and the purpose of the study was to assess which sub variable of the stakeholder management process would have a positive effect.

Figure 1.1: Conceptual Framework

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design, primarily utilizing a cross-sectional, correlational, and survey-based approach. The target group for this study consisted of 12,585 stakeholders from the 63 recognized TVETs in Western Kenya. A sample size of 375 was deemed appropriate for this study. The questionnaire was utilized to collect primary data, while document analysis was employed to gather existing qualitative data. Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

3. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Descriptive Statistics for Knowledge Sharing

Detailed results are presented in the following subsections. Knowledge sharing in Technical, Vocational, and Educational (TVET) institutions was sought in western Kenya. The respondents were asked to state about the communication methods generally used in their higher education projects, and the answers were as presented in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Common Methods used in Dissemination of Information in CSRPs

Method	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	Mean	% Mean	SD
Electronic Mail	23%	8%	44%	18%	7%	2.77	55%	1.186
Website/Online Portal	18%	6%	46%	18%	13%	3.03	61%	1.211
Meetings	1%	3%	27%	39%	30%	3.94	79%	0.884
Social media	13%	11%	44%	21%	10%	3.04	61%	1.13
Print Media	5%	11%	42%	18%	24%	3.46	69%	1.164

From the findings of Table 4.19, the study noted 44% of the respondents stated that electronic mail is only but sometimes used to disseminate information in the TVETs. The level of use of electronic mail in dissemination of information was 55% rated average (sometimes) as indicated by Mean= 2.77, Std. Deviation= 1.186. The mean and standard deviation show that respondents were few who stated that 46% stated that Website or online portal is only but sometimes used to disseminate information in the TVETs.

The level of use of Website or online portal in dissemination of information was 61% rated (often) as indicated by Mean= 3.03, Std. Deviation= 1.211. Based on Table 1.1 findings, 30% of the respondents stated that meetings are often used to disseminate information in the TVETs. The level of use of meetings in dissemination of information was 79% rated (often used) as indicated by Mean= 3.94, Std. Deviation= 0.884. As per the findings presented, 44% of the respondents stated that social media is only but sometimes used to disseminate information in the TVETs. The level of use of social media in dissemination of information was 61% rated (often used) as indicated by Mean= 3.04, Std. Deviation= 1.13. The findings also showed that 42% of the respondents, stated that print media is only but sometimes used to disseminate information in the TVETs. The level of use of print media in dissemination of information was 69% rated (often used) as indicated by Mean= 3.46, Std. Deviation= 1.164.

Table 1.2: Sharing Information in CSRPs with Stakeholders

	Very Large Extend	Large Extend	Moderate Extend	Small Extend	Very Small Extend	Mean	% Mean	SD
Sponsors	33%	48%	13%	3%	3%	1.95	39%	0.913
H.O. Ds	29%	48%	10%	12%	1%	2.08	42%	0.981
Beneficiaries	19%	13%	14%	15%	38%	3.4	68%	1.556
Small Management Teams	19%	45%	13%	14%	10%	2.51	50%	1.228
Project Management Teams	30%	47%	16%	5%	3%	2.04	41%	0.955

48% of the respondents stated that "TVETs shared information on CSRPs with sponsors to a large extent", as per the findings presented in Table 1.2, while the level of sharing the information was 39% rated below average (rarely) as indicated by Mean= 1.95, Std. Deviation= 0.913. Most of the respondents, 48% stated that TVETs shared information on CSRPs with H.O. Ds to a large extent. The level of sharing the information was 42% rated below average (rarely) as indicated by Mean= 2.08, Std. Deviation= 0.981. As per the findings, 38% of the respondents, stated that TVETs shared information on CSRPs

with beneficiaries to a very small extent. The level of sharing the information was 68% rated above average (often used) as indicated by Mean= 3.40, Std. Deviation= 1.556. The findings also revealed that 45% of the respondents agreed that TVETs shared information on CSRPs with small management teams to a large extent. The level of sharing the information was 50% rated average (sometimes) as indicated by Mean= 2.51, Std. Deviation= 1.228. 47% of the respondents stated that TVETs shared information on CSRPs with project management teams to a large extent. The level of sharing the information was 41% rated average (rarely) as indicated by Mean= 2.04, Std. Deviation= 0.955.

From the findings, sponsors and heads of department are privy to most of the information by virtue of their positions in the project management process. Beneficiaries have the least information in the running and implementation of CSRPs while project management teams and small management teams are informed of the management practices. This is a pointer that the CSRPs are initiated and run by those sponsoring them and could jeopardize ownership of and involvement of the stakeholders.

The perception of stakeholders on the Knowledge sharing about Corporate Social Responsibility Projects in TVETs in western region of Kenya was sought. The items were measured on a 5-point Likert Scale and the findings were as presented in Table 1.3.

As presented in Table 1.3, the findings indicate 42% of the respondents stated that to a moderate extent, information governance policy in place on CSRPs in the college is effective while 32% of the respondents thought that to a small extent, information sharing strategy is in place in CSRPs. A similar percentage also noted that to a small extent if the college had any agreements with other organizations or partners to facilitate access or use information that they may be holding in their custody had been effective.

As per the findings in table 1.3, the respondents indicated that information regarding projects in the college was shared upon receiving requests. From the findings, 32% of the respondents stated that to a large extent, the college always shares information collected amongst stakeholders in the event of a crisis in the management of projects. About 29% of the respondents stated that to a small extent, the college shares available data on projects with other stakeholders and that the college uses information from coordinating meetings for stakeholder management. The findings also indicated that 33% of the respondents were of the view that to a small extent, information on projects in the respective colleges shared information via regular scheduled meetings while 39% of the respondents stated that to a small extent this information was shared whether irregular or by use of ad hoc updates.

The average level of knowledge sharing on Corporate Social Responsibility projects in TVETs in Kenya's Western region was roughly 66% [M= 3.3146, SD= 0.93630]. This suggests that respondents generally agreed that there was a significant amount of knowledge sharing on these projects in TVETs in this region of Kenya.

The findings affirm that facilitating knowledge sharing within organizations is a troublesome errand. As affirmed by Halisah *et al.*, (2021) the willingness of individuals to share and integrate their knowledge is one of the central barriers. The results demonstrate that knowledge sharing entails not just a focus, a clear goal, and one-way communication, but also the potential for information to be shared in multiple directions without a specific objective in order to cultivate trust and commitment among stakeholders.

Table 1.3: Descriptive Statistics of Knowledge Sharing among Stakeholders in CSRPs

The values in bold indicates the following categories: **5**=Very large extent, **4**= Large extent, **3** = Moderate extent, **2** = Small extent, **1** = Very small extent

Statement	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	SD
To what extent do you think information governance policy in place on CSRPs in the college is effective if it at all exists	4%	11%	42%	28%	16%	3.41	1.00
To what extent do you think information-sharing strategy is in place on CSRPs in the college if at all it exists	1%	32%	15%	31%	20%	3.37	1.17
	3%	31%	13%	32%	20%	3.36	1.21

To what extend do you think the college always share information collected amongst stakeholders in the event of a crisis in the management of projects							
If your college has any agreements with other organizations or partners to facilitate access or use of information that they may be holding in their custody, to what extend do you think it has been effective?	3%	32%	24%	23%	19%	3.22	1.17
Indicate to what extend do your college share available data on projects with other stakeholders	4%	29%	17%	31%	20%	3.35	1.20
Indicate the extent to which your college uses information from co-ordinating meetings for stakeholder management.	4%	29%	21%	29%	17%	3.27	1.17
To what extend is information on projects in your college shared upon requests?	4%	32%	15%	35%	16%	3.27	1.17
To what extend is information on projects in your college shared via regular scheduled meetings?	11%	33%	14%	26%	16%	3.05	1.31
To what extend is information on projects in your college shared whether irregular/Ad Hoc updates?	5%	39%	13%	31%	11%	3.06	1.17
Average Extends of Knowledge Sharing	Mean = 3.3146 (66%%), SD = 0.93630						

Document Analysis

Secondary data from the sampled TVETs was collected on different CSRPs initiated in the institution, specific functions and sustainability issues using Document analysis form for content analysis. Muluka (2023) opines that for purposes of examining data and interpreting to elicit meaning to support evidence drawn from analysis of the questionnaire, content analysis can be used as a systematic evaluation of the study. In this case, documents containing words and images recorded without a researcher's intervention are examined and interpreted to elicit meaning. Content analysis on stakeholder management plans, risk management, stakeholder identification forms was performed.

As to whether the TVETs in Western Kenya were monitoring the sustainability of the CSRPs in the respective institutions, Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) reports were checked as evidence of monitoring and evaluating the projects among TVETs, to determine their sustainability level. It takes into account inter-related socio-economic, cultural and human health impacts both beneficial and adverse. The findings were as presented in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4: Availability of EIA Reports

Construct	No. of sampled TVETs	Evidence of EIA reports	No evidence of EIA reports	Total
Sustainability of CSRPs	40	76%	24%	100%

As presented in Table 1.4, majority of the sampled TVETs, 76% were able to provide EIA reports as evidence of monitoring and evaluating the sustainability of the CSRPs. It follows that, in accordance with their statutory obligations under Corporate Social Responsibility, majority of the institutions that support CSRPs conduct due diligence before establishing programs and initiatives. The results are consistent with the impact of corporate institutions on the long-term viability of CSRPs. Nonetheless, the participation of all stakeholders is necessary to successfully implement the recommendations of EIA assessments.

On average 24% of the TVETs did not furnish EIA reports to demonstrate the assessment of project sustainability. This absence could suggest a lack of EIA implementation or a failure to share these reports with relevant stakeholders in the TVETs. The concept of sustainability, as outlined by the World Commission on Environment and Development in 1987, refers to advancements that fulfill current requirements without jeopardizing the capacity of future generations to do the same.

Attending to future needs necessitates, among various factors, the prudent utilization of natural resources and the consideration of environmental impacts, aspects that are comprehensively documented in Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) reports. Moreover, the notion of sustainable development is frequently considered to provide a detailed examination of the intricate relationship between economic pursuits and the preservation of natural resources. This underscores the essential connection these reports hold with the sustainability objectives of the EIA process.

As to whether the TVETs in Western Kenya were able to account for their stakeholders through filling stakeholder Identification forms, the sampled TVETs were asked to furnish proof of completed Stakeholder identification documents and the findings were as presented in Table 1.5.

Table 1.5: Availability of Stakeholder Identification Forms

Construct	No. of sampled TVETs	Evidence of filled stakeholder identification forms	No Evidence of filled stakeholder identification forms	Total
Stakeholder Identification	40	72%	28%	100%

As illustrated in Table 1.5, majority of the sampled TVETs, 72% were able to provide filled stakeholder identification forms as evidence of identification of their respective stakeholders. The results suggest that identifying stakeholders in newly launched Corporate Social Responsibility Programs (CSRPs) is a practice that, when properly executed, can affect the longevity of these CSRPs. However, approximately 28% of the Technical and Vocational Education and Training institutions (TVETs) failed to produce forms for stakeholder identification, which are typically used to document stakeholder details.

This reflects a deficient process in managing stakeholders from the beginning, given that identifying stakeholders is essential for any project undertaken. Silvius and Schipper (2019) concur that to achieve sustainability in projects, there is a necessity for further development in incorporating strategies for engaging stakeholders into decision-making frameworks and in formulating standards for distinguishing various stakeholder profiles or groups.

The sampled TVETs were asked to provide evidence of communication plan and the findings were as shown in Table 4.24.

Table 1.6: Availability of Stakeholder Communication Forms

Construct	No. of sampled TVETs	Evidence of filled communication plans	No Evidence of filled communication plans	Total
Stakeholder Communication	40	79%	21%	100%

Reflected in Table 1.6, a significant portion of the evaluated TVETS, constituting 79%, demonstrated the ability to present a communication plan, suggesting that projects green-lit for funding possess a clear framework for managing communication. The data further suggests a link between the management of communication and the execution of CSRPs within TVET institutions. Conversely, 21% of the TVETs lacked the capability to showcase a communication strategy. Those TVETs devoid of a communication framework typically carried out projects with inadequate management, signifying that details regarding CSRPs may not effectively reach all involved stakeholders. According to Yazici (2020), stakeholders evolve their approaches over time and can gain sway over their objectives by collaborating with others in increasingly intricate and fluid situations. Such adaptations are facilitated by the presence of robust communication plans.

The study assessed whether the TVETs in Western Kenya have a risk management plan. Risk management plans help project managers anticipate risks, assess impacts, and define countermeasures to risks. The sampled TVETs were asked to provide evidence of the risk management plan and the findings were as presented in Table 1.7.

Table 1.7: Availability of Risk Management Plans

Construct	No. of sampled TVETs	Evidence of filled Risk Management plans	No Evidence of filled Risk management plans	Total
Stakeholder Engagement	40	83%	17%	100%

From the results presented in Table 1.7, the majority of the sampled TVETs, 83% were able to provide a risk management plan. The plan was annexed to the projects proposals in the respective offices. However, most stakeholders neglected to consider whether they were fully implemented during the creation and execution of CSRPs. About 17% of the TVETs were not able to provide evidence of a risk management plan. Most of the respondents failed to grasp the essence of a risk management plan, prompting questions about the extent of knowledge sharing in the projects that were launched. As Doskočil and Lacko (2018) point out, risk occurs when there is a vulnerability in an organization's operating system without adequate countermeasures and controls in place (i.e., a lack of risk management). The most effective way to address this issue is through the development and implementation of robust risk management plans.

The study sought to assess whether the TVETs in Western Kenya have Project Issue Log. The main purpose of this log was to determine if there was proper documentation of potential hazards that could lead to project-related risks. The Issue Log consists of a comprehensive list of both ongoing and resolved issues within the project. The selected TVETs were requested to provide evidence of their Project Issue Log, and the results were as presented in Table 1.8.

Table 1.8: Availability of Project Issues Log Plans

Construct	No. of sampled TVETs	Evidence of filled Project issues log	No Evidence of filled project issues log	Total
Stakeholder Empowerment	40	85%	15%	100%

The findings as captured in Table 1.8 indicated that majority of the sampled TVETs, 85% were able to avail a Project Issue Log. However, it is worth noting that these logs were not properly filled out, indicating that most of the hazards and risks associated with the projects were not documented. The evidence suggests that the sponsors and TVETs took the lead in executing the projects, with little to no contribution from the stakeholders. This was noted by the 15% of TVETs that were unable to produce a project issue log as proof. This is seen by Civera *et al.*, (2019) as an attempt to mollify stakeholders by project managers while focusing their attention on the details of project management rather than to empower stakeholders to have a significant input to the project empowerment being seen to encourage 'interference' from non-specialists into the managers' domain.

Assessment of whether the TVETs in Western Kenya have stakeholder analysis register was made. The Stakeholder Analysis Register plays a crucial role in compiling pertinent information about all stakeholders, groups, and organizations that demonstrate an interest or involvement in the CSRPs. Moreover, it provides a clear understanding of stakeholder expectations in relation to the established projects. The sampled TVETs were asked to provide evidence of stakeholder analysis register and the findings were as presented in Table 1.9.

Table 1.9: Availability of Stakeholder Analysis Register

Construct	No. of sampled TVETs	Evidence of filled stakeholder analysis register	No Evidence of filled stakeholder analysis register	Total
Knowledge Sharing	40	68%	32%	100%

The findings as presented in Table 1.9 indicate that majority of the sampled TVETs, 68% were able to avail a Stakeholder Analysis register but in some of the project proposals, the registers were not duly filled raising questions its functionality in the management of projects. About 32% of the TVETs were not able to avail evidence of a Stakeholder Analysis register. This implies that the information was not widely shared to all stakeholders and beneficiaries of the projects were not included in the stakeholder analysis register. The findings indicate availability of stakeholder analysis registers on paper but are not actualised in the implementation of CSRPs. The findings of Hargrove and Heyman (2020) underscore the influential role of stakeholders in the achievement of objectives. It is crucial to identify the relevant stakeholders for sustainability in order to ensure the successful implementation of sustainability initiatives within a specific context.

Reliability Analysis for Knowledge Sharing

To assess the reliability of the scale employed for measuring knowledge sharing on the Social Corporate Projects in the TVETs in Western Kenya, the study utilized Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient. The standard reliability coefficient was derived from Nunnally and Bernstein (1994), who proposed that for preliminary research on predictor tests or hypothesized measures of a construct, reliabilities of .70 or above would be satisfactory. The pilot test results were as presented in Table 2.0.

Table 2.0 Descriptive Summary of Reliability Analysis

Construct	No. of Items	Mean (SD)	Skewness	Cronbach's Alpha
Knowledge sharing on Social Corporate Projects	9	2.38 (.88)	0.42	0.74

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for knowledge sharing on Social Corporate Project construct, as presented in Table 2.0, was calculated to be 0.74. This value surpasses the lower limit of acceptability at 0.6 (Hair *et al.*, 2006) and falls within the recommended range of 0.70 and above by Nunnally (1978), indicating that the scale is reliable and suitable for further analysis.

Factor Analysis for Knowledge sharing on Social Corporate Project

To evaluate the construct validity of the Knowledge Sharing construct, Principal Component Analysis was employed. A principal components analysis with Varimax rotation was carried out on 11 items to determine factor loadings and communalities, resulting in a well-defined factor structure for the Knowledge Sharing on Social Corporate Project construct. The findings are detailed in Table 2.1.

All communalities as presented in table 1.3 exceeded the 0.3 threshold, indicating shared variance among items on the 5-point Likert scale. Moreover, all eleven items demonstrated primary loadings above .5, confirming that the data was acceptable and valid for further analysis.

Table 2.1 Factor Analysis on knowledge sharing on Social Corporate Project

Item	Factor loading	Communality
To what extend do you think information governance policy in place on SCPs in the college is effective if it at all exists	.771	.37
To what extend do you think information-sharing strategy in place on SCPs in the college if at all it exists	.767	.36
To what extend do you think the college always share information collected amongst stakeholders in the event of a crisis in the management of projects	.753	.43
If your college has any agreements with other organizations or partners to facilitate access or use of information that they may be holding in their custody, to what extend do you think it has been effective?	.710	.54
Indicate to what extend do your college share available data on projects with other stakeholders	.699	.65
Indicate the extent to which your college uses information from coordinating meetings for stakeholder management.	.673	.33
To what extend is information on projects in your college shared upon requests?	.651	.45
To what extend is information on projects in your college shared via regular scheduled meetings?	.644	.38
To what extend is information on projects in your college shared whether irregular/Ad Hoc updates?	.598	.64

Normality test

To assess the assumption of normal distribution regarding Knowledge sharing on Social Corporate Projects, the Shapiro-Wilk test was utilized in this study. The null hypothesis proposed that the scores for Knowledge sharing on Social Corporate Projects were not significantly distinct from a normal distribution. The results of this examination were as presented in table 2.2.

Table 2.2. Normality test for Distribution of scores for Knowledge sharing on Social Corporate Projects

	Shapiro-Wilk test		
	Statistic	Df	p-value
Knowledge Sharing	.930	355	.087

Based on the Shapiro Wilk test results presented in table 2.2, it was found that the p-value of 0.087 is greater than the significance level of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, leading to the conclusion that the scores for knowledge sharing on the Social Corporate Project were significantly normally distributed.

Correlation Analysis

The study investigated the correlation between stakeholder management process, specifically stakeholder identification, stakeholder engagement, stakeholder communication, and stakeholder empowerment, as well as knowledge sharing and the sustainability of projects. Pearson product moment correlation analysis was employed to analyse the composite means of variables. The findings of the analysis were outlined as presented in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3: Correlation Analysis

Correlations		SUS	KS	SID	SCom	SEng	SEmp
1	Sustainability (SUS)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 352				
	Knowledge						
2	Sharing (KS)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.725** <0.001 347	1 <0.001 355			
3	Stakeholders Identification (SID)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.596** <0.001 350	.596** <0.001 352	1 <0.001 359		
4	Stakeholder Communication (SCom)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.583** <0.001 351	.441** <0.001 353	.618** <0.001 358	1 <0.001 362	
5	Stakeholder Engagement (SEng)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.691** <0.001 346	.672** <0.001 348	.612** <0.001 353	.739** <0.001 354	1 <0.001 355
6	Stakeholder Empowerment (SEmp)	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.617** <0.001 350	.602** <0.001 352	.552** <0.001 356	.793** <0.001 357	.815** <0.001 353
							1 358

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlations highlighted in bold as presented in table 2.3, represent the strength of the relationship between sustainability (SUS) and the stakeholder management processes. The most robust relationship was observed between knowledge sharing (KS) and sustainability ($r=0.725$, $p<0.001 < 0.05$), followed by the relationship between sustainability and stakeholder engagement (SEng) ($r=0.691$, $p<0.001 < 0.05$). On the other hand, the weakest relationship was found between stakeholder communication (SCom) and sustainability ($r=0.583$, $p<0.001 < 0.05$). It is worth noting that all the relationships were positive and significant ($p<0.001$), indicating that stakeholder management processes were strongly and significantly associated with sustainability.

The adoption of knowledge management practices and the performance of firms are strongly and positively correlated, according to empirical research by Maende (2021). Knowledge sharing in organizations is positively correlated with trust, communication, information systems, rewards, and organizational structure, according to the findings. In order to support community members in sharing their expertise and to encourage individuals to contribute their personal knowledge, fairness, identification, and openness are considered as important strategies (Nguyen & Mohamed, 2020). Concerning the explanation of sustainability in CSRPs, these factors are related to the degree of knowledge sharing and stakeholder identification. Low stakeholder communication and CSRPs sustainability are related to the above projects' inadequate knowledge sharing. These results are consistent with those of Ndombi (2021b), who found a significant positive and

moderate correlation between stakeholder management and the sustainability of donor-funded livelihood projects in Kilifi County, with stakeholder management having a major impact on the sustainability of these projects.

Moderation Analysis

Moderation analysis is conducted to investigate if the moderator (Knowledge sharing) alters the degree to which the independent (Stakeholder Management Process) and dependent (Sustainability of Corporate Social Responsibility) variables are related. The moderation effect of Knowledge sharing on the relationship between Stakeholder identification, Stakeholder communication, Stakeholder engagement and Stakeholder empowerment and Sustainability of Corporate Social Responsibility Projects was as presented in Table 2.4.

Table 2.4: Summary of the Regression Analysis and Moderation Analysis

Model summary	Stakeholder Identification		Stakeholder Communication		Stakeholder Engagement		Stakeholder Empowerment	
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 1	Model 2	Model 1	Model 2	Model 1	Model 2
R	0.596	0.598	0.583	0.624	0.691	0.691	0.617	0.617
R Square	0.355	0.357	0.34	0.389	0.478	0.478	0.381	0.381
Adjusted R Square	0.354	0.354	0.338	0.385	0.476	0.475	0.379	0.377
Std. Error	0.53125	0.5341	0.53753	0.52057	0.47829	0.47774	0.52058	0.51877
ANOVA								
Degrees of freedom (<i>a,b</i>)	(1, 348)	(2, 342)	(1, 349)	(2, 343)	(1, 344)	(2, 338)	(1, 348)	(2, 342)
F- statistic, <i>F(a,b)</i>	191.924	95.082	179.892	109.091	314.468	154.713	214.275	105.266
p-value for F- statistic	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
F-Change statistic		0.677		23.563		0.078		0.038
p-value for F- Change statistic		0.411		0.000		0.780		0.845
Regression Coefficients								
Intercept	1.731	3.406	2.053	3.463	1.215	1.266	1.780	3.405
β (Unstandardized coefficient)	0.515	0.387	0.439	0.368	0.622	0.612	0.493	0.402
Standardized Beta Coefficient	0.596	0.588	0.583	0.549	0.691	0.685	0.617	0.612
<i>t</i> (β)	13.854	13.157	13.412	12.772	17.733	15.217	14.638	12.324
p-value (β)	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
<i>t</i> (Intercept)	14.030	93.980	19.723	111.935	9.676	8.110	15.641	95.897
p-value (Intercept)	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Interaction Effect								
β (Unstandardized coefficient)		-0.030		-0.151		-0.010		-0.007
Standardized Beta Coefficient		-0.037		-0.209		-0.013		-0.010
<i>t</i> (β)		-0.823		-4.854		-0.279		-0.195
p-value (β)		0.411		0.000		0.780		0.845

The outcomes of the basic linear regression are represented by Model 1. Model 2 uses hierarchical linear regression to represent the moderation analysis results. From the findings as presented in Table 2.4, Knowledge Sharing had no discernible moderating effect on the relationship between Stakeholder Identification and Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya. The Interaction Effect did not significantly affect the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya [R^2 change = .001, F-change =0.677, β = -0.030, t =-0.823 p =0.411>0.05]. Knowledge sharing had no significant moderation effect on the relationship between Stakeholder Engagement and Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs, as evidenced by the Interaction Effect's lack of significant impact on the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETS in Western Kenya [R^2 change = .000, F-change =0.078, β = -0.010, t =-0.013, p =0.780>0.05].

The same was true for Stakeholder Empowerment, as the Interaction Effect did not show a significant impact on the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya [R^2 change = .000, F-change =0.038, β = -0.007, t =-0.195,

$p=0.845>0.05$]. This suggests that Knowledge Sharing did not play a significant moderating role in the connection between Stakeholder Empowerment and Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya. In contrast, the Interaction Effect did have a significant impact on the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya [R^2 change = .042, F-change =23.563, $\beta = -0.151$, $t = -4.854$ $p=0.00<0.05$], indicating that Knowledge Sharing did have a significant moderating effect on the relationship between Stakeholder Communication and Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya.

The above findings mirror a study conducted by Nyambura (2018), where it was discovered that all independent variables in the study, except for organizational characteristics, did not significantly predict the performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. However, the model analyzing the joint moderation effect of ICT use on the relationship between supply chain risks and firm performance was found to be significant, potentially due to organizational characteristic risk. In this investigation, the moderation effect of knowledge sharing is deemed significant when focusing on stakeholder communication and the sustainability of CSRPs.

The moderating effect was tested using stepwise analysis.

Moderation effect of Knowledge Sharing on the relationship between Stakeholder Identification and Sustainability of CSRPs was tested using the null hypothesis:

H₀₁: Knowledge Sharing does not moderate the relationship between Stakeholder Identification and Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya.

The results of the Hierarchical Linear Regression analysis as presented in Table 2.4, where the comparison between model 2 (including both Stakeholder Identification and Interaction term) and model 1 (including only Stakeholder Identification) is shown. Based on the data in Table 2.4, it was found that the Interaction Effect did not have a significant impact on the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya [R^2 change = .001, F-change =0.677, $\beta = -0.030$, $t =-0.823$ $p=0.411>0.05$]. This implies that Knowledge Sharing did not play a significant moderating role in the relationship between Stakeholder Identification and Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya.

To predict Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya, given level of Stakeholder Identification in the presence of Knowledge Sharing as moderator is given:

Sustainability of CSRPs = 3.406 + 0.387 Stakeholder Identification – 0.030 IE

Where;

IE = Interaction Effect

The findings align with previous research that demonstrates the influence of the subconscious dimension on knowledge management, as indicated by S. Li et al. (2022). Consequently, the intangible nature of power, interest, and network acknowledgment makes it challenging to differentiate them from their human owners, thereby complicating stakeholder identification (Maende, 2021). It is widely agreed upon that stakeholder power and interest are expected to have a significant correlation with the implementation of stakeholder management strategies (Nguyen & Mohamed, 2020).

To test moderation effect of Knowledge Sharing on the relationship between Stakeholder Communication and Sustainability of CSRPs, the null hypothesis stated was:

H₀₂; Knowledge sharing does not moderate the relationship between stakeholder communication and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in western Kenya.

The outcomes of the moderation analysis carried out using Hierarchical Linear Regression were displayed as presented in Table 2.4. This table illustrates the comparison between the results of model 2 (where both Stakeholder Communication and Interaction term were included simultaneously) and model 1 (which solely featured Stakeholder Identification) as shown in Table 2.4. Based on the findings in Table 2.4, the Interaction Effect significantly influenced the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya [R^2 change = .042, F-change =23.563, $\beta = -0.151$, $t = -4.854$ $p=0.00<0.05$]. This indicates that Knowledge Sharing had a notable moderating impact on the association between Stakeholder Communication and the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya.

To predict Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya, given level of Stakeholder Communication in the presence of Knowledge Sharing as moderator is given:

$$\text{Sustainability of CSRPs} = 3.463 + 0.368 \text{ Stakeholder Communication} - 0.151 \text{ IE}$$

Where;

IE = Interaction Effect

To provide additional confirmation of the substantial impact of stakeholder communication as a moderation factor, the moderation results were investigated through the use of graphical plots. These plots were utilized to analyze the variations in slope regarding the influence of stakeholder communication on the sustainability of CSRPs at different levels of the moderator. The objective of this graphical probing was to illustrate that the slopes of the graphs at each level of the hypothesized moderator exhibit significant differences. To examine the moderation effect of Knowledge Sharing on the relationship between Stakeholder Communication and Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya, an interaction plot was generated and presented in Figure 1.2.

By analysing the interaction plot as presented in Figure 1.2, the study discovered that Knowledge Sharing had a significant moderating effect on the association between Stakeholder Communication and the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya. Notably, when the level of Knowledge Sharing was low, Stakeholder Communication exerted a stronger influence on the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya compared to the moderate and high levels of Knowledge Sharing.

Figure 1.2: Interaction plot of Knowledge Sharing and Stakeholder Communication

The graphical representation in Figure 1.2 and the data presented in Table 2.4 demonstrate that when the level of Knowledge Sharing was moderate, Stakeholder Communication had a stronger influence on the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya compared to situations with low levels of Knowledge Sharing. However, as the level of stakeholder communication improved, the moderation effect seemed to diminish. These findings align with the research conducted by Shehab *et al.* (2018), which highlighted the significant contribution of stakeholder communication to the general knowledge sharing behavior of nursing supervisors in online healthcare communities. Furthermore, studies conducted by Nyandika and Ngugi (2014) and Ndombi (2021b) confirmed that stakeholder participation influenced the performance of road projects that extended beyond donor funding and the sustainability of donor-funded livelihood projects in Kilifi. Specifically, the constructs related to stakeholder management indicated that both knowledge sharing ($P= 0.0002 < 0.05$) and stakeholder communication ($P= 0.039 < 0.05$) significantly contributed to sustainability.

Moderation effect of Knowledge Sharing on the relationship between Stakeholder Engagement and Sustainability of CSRPs was tested and the null hypothesis was;

H₀₃; *Knowledge sharing does not moderate the relationship between stakeholder engagement and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in western Kenya.*

The results of the moderation analysis using Hierarchical Linear Regression were detailed as presented in Table 2.4. Here, the comparison was made between the outcomes of model 2 (which included both Stakeholder Engagement and Interaction term) and the results of model 1, where only Stakeholder Engagement was considered.

Based on the findings as presented in Table 2.4, it was concluded that the Interaction Effect did not have a significant impact on the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya [R^2 change = .000, F-change =0.078, β = -0.010, t =-0.013, $p=0.780>0.05$]. These results indicate that Knowledge Sharing did not play a significant moderating role in the relationship between Stakeholder Engagement and the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya. To predict Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya, given level of Stakeholder Engagement in the presence of Knowledge Sharing as moderator is given:

$$\text{Sustainability of CSRPs} = 1.266 + 0.612 \text{ Stakeholder Engagement} - 0.010 \text{ IE}$$

Where; **IE** = Interaction Effect

The above findings align with the study on the mediation effects of stakeholder management between stakeholder characteristics and project performance. This study indicates that agile methods are greatly reliant on early and continuous stakeholder involvement, encompassing feedback provision and goal setting for projects throughout the project life cycle (Nguyen & Mohamed, 2020). The study uncovered a strong connection between key stakeholders and project flexibility. Hence, effective stakeholder management through agile engagement is deemed crucial, contingent upon the successful identification of stakeholders.

Moderation effect of Knowledge Sharing on the relationship between Stakeholder Empowerment and Sustainability of CSRPs was examined and the null hypothesis was:

H₀₄; *Knowledge sharing does not moderate the relationship between stakeholder empowerment and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya.*

The results of the moderation analysis carried out using Hierarchical Linear Regression were presented in Table 2.4, where the comparison between the model 2 results (with both Stakeholder Empowerment and Interaction term) and the model 1 results (containing only Stakeholder Empowerment) was presented. From the findings in Table 2.4, the Interaction Effect did not have a significant influence on the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya [R^2 change = .000, F-change =0.038, β = -0.007, t =-0.195, $p=0.845>0.05$]; indicating that Knowledge Sharing had no significant moderation effect on the relationship between Stakeholder Empowerment and Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya. To predict Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya, given level of Stakeholder Empowerment in the presence of Knowledge Sharing as moderator is given;

$$\text{Sustainability of CSRPs} = 3.405 + 0.402 \text{ Stakeholder Empowerment} - 0.010 \text{ IE}$$

Where; **IE** = Interaction Effect

The findings align with Maende's (2021) study, which emphasizes that stakeholder empowerment is contingent upon providing professional support to organizational members, in this case stakeholders. This support includes facilitating the free flow of information, ensuring clarity of instructions, continuously reviewing, and enhancing recurring tasks, and employing transparent coordination techniques. Maende recommends the adoption of knowledge management practices to enhance institutional accountability. The handling of knowledge management by institutions is crucial for ensuring legitimacy and risk control.

The study conducted by Ndombi (2021b) presents results that bear resemblance to the findings regarding the moderation effect of knowledge sharing on the relationship between stakeholder management process and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs. Similarly, Ndombi's study examined the moderating influence of stakeholder management on the relationship between project exit strategies and sustainability of donor funded projects in Kilifi County. However, the study discovered

no significant moderating influence. Notably, the significance of the relationship emerged when assessing the causal relationship between stakeholder management and sustainability. Moderation analysis in the study has been summarised as presented in Table 2.5 as below:

Table 2.5: A Summary of Moderation Analysis

Hypothesis	Interaction Effect	Decision
H_{05a} Knowledge sharing does not moderate the relationship between stakeholder identification and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in western Kenya	[R^2 change = .001, F -change = 0.677, β = -0.030, t = -0.823 p = 0.411 > 0.05]	Accept
H_{05b} Knowledge sharing does not moderate the relationship between stakeholder communication and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in western Kenya	[R^2 change = .042, F -change = 23.563, β = -0.151, t = -4.854 p = 0.00 < 0.05]	Rejected
H_{05c} Knowledge sharing does not moderate the relationship between stakeholder engagement and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in western Kenya	[R^2 change = .000, F -change = 0.078, β = -0.010, t = -0.013, p = 0.780 > 0.05]	Accept
H_{05d} Knowledge sharing does not moderate the relationship between stakeholder empowerment and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in western Kenya	[R^2 change = .000, F -change = 0.038, β = -0.007, t = -0.195, p = 0.845 > 0.05]	Accept

Optimal Model

Based on the research findings presented in the study, the revised study model, depicted in Figure 1.3, considers the significance of the coefficients for the combined study variables in relation to the sustainability of CSRPs. The Multiple Linear Regression model equation used to estimate the sustainability of CSRPs in Western Kenya, considering the stakeholder management processes (Stakeholder Identification [SID], Communication [SCom], Engagement [SEng], and Empowerment [SEmp]), is as follows: **SUS (Sustainability) = 1.007 + 0.240 SID (Stakeholder Identification) + 0.376 SEng (Stakeholder Engagement)**. Furthermore, during the moderation analysis, it was found that Knowledge Sharing significantly moderates the relationship between Stakeholder Engagement and the sustainability of CSRPs.

Figure 1.3: Revised Study Model

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The objective of the study was to examine the influence of knowledge sharing as a moderator on the relationship between Stakeholder Identification, Stakeholder Communication, Stakeholder Engagement and Stakeholder Empowerment on the sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in western Kenya. That knowledge sharing has a statistically significant moderating effect on stakeholder management process and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs. Knowledge sharing had a significant moderation effect on the relationship between stakeholder communication and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in western Kenya. Equally, Knowledge sharing had no significant moderation influence between stakeholder empowerment and sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in western Kenya. The results indicate that knowledge sharing can only be effective if organizational members in this case, stakeholders are accorded professional support in their day-to-day activities which include free flow of information, clarity of instructions, constant review and improvement of recurring tasks and transparent coordination techniques and therefore recommending for implementation of knowledge management practices policy to improve institutional accountability. Legitimacy and Risk control is enshrined in the manner in which knowledge management will be handled by the institutions. Trust, information systems established in the CSRPs, and motivation are the main constructs of knowledge sharing that explain for the changes observed in the sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in western Kenya.

The study revealed that Knowledge Sharing demonstrated an enhancing moderation effect on the relationship between Stakeholder Communication and Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya. When the level of Knowledge Sharing was low, Stakeholder Communication seemed to have a higher influence on the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya compared to moderate and low levels of Knowledge Sharing. When the level of Knowledge Sharing was moderate, Stakeholder Communication seemed to have a higher influence on the Sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs in Western Kenya compared to low levels of knowledge sharing. In conclusion, the study establishes that the joint effect of stakeholder identification and stakeholder engagement, moderated by knowledge sharing, has a more substantial influence on the sustainability of CSRPs compared to the separate effects of the predictor variables. To enhance the sustainability of CSRPs in TVETs, the study recommends providing stakeholders with training on effective stakeholder communication and engagement, thereby strengthening the stakeholder management process.

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

This study makes significant contributions to knowledge in various aspects. Firstly, it confirms the effectiveness of the stakeholder management process in the specific context of Kenya. Secondly, it specifically examines the stakeholder management process in TVETs in Kenya, which sets it apart from previous studies that only mention stakeholder management practices in general. Thirdly, it addresses a knowledge gap by incorporating knowledge sharing as a moderator in the relationship between the predictor and predicted variables. Knowledge sharing practice plays a crucial role in the intervention of stakeholder management process.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abdelwhab Ali, A., Panneer selvam, D. D. D., Paris, L., & Gunasekaran, A. (2019). Key Factors influencing Knowledge sharing practices and its relationship with Organizational Performance within the Oil and Gas industry. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 23(9), 1806–1837.
- [2] Al-Kurdi, O. F., El-Haddadeh, R., & Eldabi, T. (2020). The role of organisational climate in managing knowledge sharing among academics in higher education. *International Journal of Information Management*, 50, 217–227.
- [3] Amenta, E., & Ramsey, K. M. (2010). Institutional theory. In *Handbook of politics* (pp. 15–39). Springer.
- [4] Civera, C., Colle, S. de, & Casalegno, C. (2019). Stakeholder engagement through empowerment: The case of coffee farmers. *Business Ethics: A European Review*, 28(2), 156–174.
- [5] Deichmann, D., Moser, C., & van den Ende, J. (2021). Talk, talk, talk: Exploring idea conversations and the micro-level foundations of knowledge sharing for innovation. *Innovation*, 23(3), 287–313.
- [6] Doskočil, R., & Lacko, B. (2018). Risk Management and Knowledge Management as Critical Success Factors of Sustainability Projects. *Sustainability*, 10(5), 1438.

- [7] Fayyaz, A., Chaudhry, B. N., & Fiaz, M. (2021). Upholding Knowledge Sharing for Organization Innovation Efficiency in Pakistan. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(1), 1-17.
- [8] Foss, N. J., Husted, K., & Michailova, S. (2010). Governing knowledge sharing in organizations: Levels of analysis, governance mechanisms, and research directions. *Journal of Management Studies*, 47(3), 455–482.
- [9] Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Tatham, R. L. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis (Vol. 8)*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [10] Hargrove, W. L., & Heyman, J. M. (2020). A comprehensive process for stakeholder identification and engagement in addressing wicked water resources problems. *Land*, 9(4), 119.
- [11] Halisah, A., Jayasingam, S., Ramayah, T., & Popa, S. (2021). Social dilemmas in knowledge sharing: an examination of the interplay between knowledge sharing culture and performance climate. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 25(7), 1708-1725.
- [12] Herold, D. M. (2018). Demystifying the link between institutional theory and stakeholder theory in sustainability reporting. *Economics, Management and Sustainability*, 3(2), 6–19.
- [13] Kariuki, J. M. (2014). *Factors influencing Sustainability of Non-Government Organizations funded community projects in Kenya: A case of Action aid funded project in Makima location, Embu County* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi].
- [14] Lam, A., & Lambermont-Ford, J.-P. (2010). Knowledge sharing in organizational contexts: A motivation-based perspective. *Journal of Knowledge Management* 14(1), 51-66.
- [15] Maende, B. M. (2021). *Knowledge Management Practices and Employee Performance in Public Universities in Kenya* [Doctoral dissertation, JKUAT-COHRED].
- [16] Muluka, K. O. (2023). *Project Management Practices and Success Factors of Digital Literacy Programme in Western Kenya* [Doctoral dissertation, JKUAT-COHRED].
- [17] Ndombi, C. L. (2021a). *Project Exit Strategies, Stakeholders Management, and Project Sustainability of Donor-funded Livelihood Projects in Kilifi County, Kenya* [Masters' dissertation, University of Nairobi].
- [18] Ndombi, C. L. (2021b). *Project Exit Strategies, Stakeholders Management, and Project Sustainability of Donor-funded Livelihood Projects in Kilifi County, Kenya* [Thesis, University of Nairobi]. Retrieved from <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/155700>.
- [19] Nguyen, T. S., & Mohamed, S. (2020). Mediation Effect of Stakeholder Management between Stakeholder Characteristics and Project Performance. *Journal of Engineering Project and Production Management*, 11, 102–117.
- [20] Nyambura, M. T. (2018). *Moderating Effect of Information Communication Technology on Supply Chain Risks and Firm Performance among Manufacturing Firms in Kenya* [Thesis, JKUAT]. Retrieved from <http://localhost/xmlui/handle/123456789/4577>.
- [21] Oliveira, M. J. S. P., & Pinheiro, P. (2020). Factors and Barriers to Tacit Knowledge Sharing in Non-Profit Organizations – a Case Study of Volunteer Firefighters in Portugal. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*. 12(3), 1294–1313.
- [22] Oloo, O. (2003). HIV/AIDS: Corporate Social Responsibility. Market Intelligence, *The Business and Financial Journal*, November/December, Pg15.
- [23] Park, H. S., & Lee, Y. H. (2016). Exploring a Process Model for Stakeholder Management. *Public Relations Journal*, 9(4), 1-17.
- [24] Paulin, D., & Suneson, K. (2012). Knowledge transfer, knowledge sharing and knowledge barriers—three blurry terms in KM. *Electronic Journal of Knowledge Management*, 10(1), 82-92.
- [25] Pearce, D.W. (2003). Environment and business: socially responsible but privately profitable? 811 In J. Hirst (ed)”. *The Challenge of Change: Fifty Years of Business Economics*, 54-65 ,812 London: Profile Books, London, UK.

- [26] Prasad, B. D. (2008). Content Analysis: A Method in Social Science Research. *Research Methods for Social Work*, 5, 1–20. New Delhi: Rawat.
- [27] Pinjani, P., & Palvia, P. (2013). Trust and knowledge sharing in diverse global virtual teams. *Information & Management*, 50(4), 144–153.
- [28] Reyshav, I., & Weisberg, J. (2010). Bridging Intention and Behavior of Knowledge Sharing. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 14(2), 285-300.
- [29] Santos, V. R., Soares, A. L., & Carvalho, J. Á. (2012). Knowledge Sharing Barriers in Complex Research and Development Projects: An Exploratory Study on the Perceptions of Project Managers: Knowledge Sharing Barriers in Complex R&D Projects. *Knowledge and Process Management*, 19(1), 27–38.
- [30] Schneiberg, M., & Lounsbury, M. (2017). Social Movements and the Dynamics of Institutions and Organizations. In *The SAGE Handbook of Organizational Institutionalism* (pp. 281-310). SAGE Publications Ltd, <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781526415066>.
- [31] Schneiberg, M., & Soule, S. A. (2005). Institutionalization As a Contested, Multilevel Process. *Social Movements and Organization Theory*, 122, 160. Cambridge, U.K.: Cambridge University Press.
- [32] Shehab, S., Eladwiah, R., & Daud, S. (2018). *A Review of Individual Factors on Knowledge Sharing: Evidence from Empirical Literature*, 7, 186–194.
- [33] Shehab, S., Rahim, R. E. A., & Daud, S. (2019). Knowledge sharing behavior of nursing supervisors in online healthcare communities. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 11(1), 1662–1678.
- [34] Torelli, R., Balluchi, F., & Furlotti, K. (2020). The Materiality Assessment and Stakeholder Engagement: A content analysis of Sustainability Reports. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 27(2), 470–484.
- [35] Tamsah, H., Ansar, Ilyas, G., Yusriadi, Y., & Farida, U. (2020). Training, Knowledge Sharing, and Quality of Work-Life on Civil Servants Performance in Indonesia. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 7, 163–176.
- [36] Toner, J., & Martins, J. T. (2021). Institutional Isomorphism in Collaborative, Cross-cultural, Project-based Development Work: An inquiry into the Knowledge Sharing Behavior of Volunteers. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 26(7), 1763-1788.
- [37] Tucker, W. E and W. J. Henkel (1992). *The legal and Ethical Environment of Business*. Richard D Irwin Inc. US.
- [38] Mc Ewan, T (2001). *Managing Values and Beliefs in Organizations*. Pearson Education Limited, Edinburgh, England.
- [39] Cavanagh, J. (2004). *Alternatives to Economic Globalization: A Better World is Possible*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- [40] Fuchs, P., & Leonhard, P. (2007). Accountability Is Based on Duties. *Corporate Social Responsibility, Development and Cooperation International Journal (D+ C)* vol, 34.
- [41] United Nations Report (1979). *1978 Report on the World Social Situation*. New York, U.N
- [42] Wang, S., & Noe, R. A. (2010). Knowledge sharing: A review and directions for future research. *Human Resource Management Review*, 20 (2), 115–131.
- [43] Wang, Z., & Wang, N. (2012). Knowledge Sharing, Innovation, And Firm Performance. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 39(10), 8899–8908.
- [44] Watetu, N. J. (2015). *Knowledge sharing, Organizational learning, firm-level institutions, and performance of top medium-sized companies in Kenya* [PhD Thesis, University of Nairobi, Kenya].
- [45] Zhao, Y., Zhang, X., Wang, J., Zhang, K., & Ordóñez de Pablos, P. (2020). How do features of Social Media influence Knowledge sharing? An ambient awareness perspective. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 24(2), 439–462.